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Instructional Design for Arabic-Korean Translation Class: Based on ChatGPT's Feedback

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Abstract

본 연구는 아랍어-한국어 번역 수업을 위해 연습(practice), 과제(assignment), 토의(discussion)의 세 단계로 구성된 수업 모형 안에서 ChatGPT를 피드백 도구로 통합한 교수·학습 설계를 제시하고자 한다. 이 설계는 한국어를 전공하는 학부생들을 대상으로 적용되었으며, 사전·사후 평가와 온라인 설문조사를 통해 그 효과를 검증하였다. 연구 결과, 문장 구조, 문법, 어휘 선택 측면에서 번역 정확도가 유의미하게 향상된 것으로 나타났으며, 이러한 향상은 학습자 수행 결과와 자기 평가 자료 모두에서 확인되었다.

주요 장점으로는 즉각적이고 접근성이 높은 피드백 제공, 오류의 정밀한 탐지, 그리고 설명이 포함된 번역 결과물이 있었다. 그러나 오류의 과잉 탐지, 동일 입력에 대한 분석의 일관성 부족, 프롬프트 표현 방식에 따른 피드백의 변동성 등의 한계도 관찰되었다. 이러한 결과는 교수자의 중재와 효과적인 프롬프트 설계에 대한 명시적 교육의 필요성을 시사한다.

본 연구는 인공지능 도구가 신중하게 통합되고 적절히 조정될 때 피드백 실행을 강화하고, 학습자 자율성을 촉진하며, 언어적 다양성이 높은 교육 환경에서도 확장 가능한 교수·학습 모형을 지원할 수 있음을 보여 줌으로써 번역 교육 분야에 학문적 기여를 한다.

1. Introduction

Translation is no longer what it used to be, as it has undergone many changes since the emergence of artificial intelligence models most notably the Large Language Model; ChatGPT, developed by OpenAI in 2022(Gao et al., 2024; Jiao et al., 2023; Lee, 2023). These tools have contributed to speeding up translation processes and providing instant translations, which has clearly impacted the traditional translation field and its conventional working methods (Al-Wasy and Mohammed, 2024; Khoshafah, 2023).

Recently, professional translators also use artificial intelligence models to translate their content or to create initial drafts of their translations, which they then review and edit to achieve the highest possible quality. This reflects how AI-based models, with their rapid development, have brought about a significant shift in the concept of translation, the way it is approached, and even how it is taught (Lee, 2023).

Recent studies have demonstrated that the use of AI-based models in the educational process has a significantly positive impact on student performance (Prasetya and Syarif 2023; Fan et al. 2023; Hasan et al. 2025). However, there remains ongoing uncertainty and debate regarding the most effective ways to integrate these models, as well as the best practices to maximize their benefits without compromising students' critical thinking skills. Moreover, some studies have indicated that the use of artificial intelligence tools raises several concerns, including the risk of plagiarism and academic inequality, as some students may gain advantages that are not equally accessible to their peers (Fan et al. 2023; Yan, 2023).

Hasan et al. 2025 has developed an instructional design for translation class for undergraduate students, which involved comparing students' own translations with those generated by AI-based model, and has revealed that many students lack the analytical, comparative, and evaluative skills required, largely because they are not accustomed to engaging in higher-order thinking. This highlights the need to develop improved pedagogical approaches that bridge this gap by switching the roles and making the AI-based models do the analytical work.

Providing effective feedback plays a crucial role in enhancing students' performance, as it

helps them understand the mistakes they made, how to correct them, and how to continually improve their skills. Feedback is an essential element of the learning process, however, many instructors face significant challenges in dedicating enough time to review all the assignments submitted by students, particularly in classes with large numbers of students (e.g. Carless 2023; Zhan 2023). Furthermore, the tasks assigned to students can be substantial in terms of quantity, making it difficult for instructors to provide timely and comprehensive feedback to each student.

This study attempts to provide an improved instructional design of the previously suggested by (Hasan et al. 2025). In this instructional design, the students are not required to evaluate, assess, and analyze. Instead, the students are required to assign ChatGPT to do this task by requiring it to provide feedback and an error analysis. Then the students will discuss ChatGPT's output with instructor. In this study, AI-based models will be used to assess students' translations. The AI tool will be prompted to analyze the student's translation, identify linguistic, contextual, or stylistic errors, and clearly indicate their locations. It will then provide an explanation for each identified error, suggest appropriate alternatives, and present an improved version of the translation.

At the beginning of this study, different AI-based models were used to gather feedback. However, a significant performance gap was observed across the models. This was particularly evident with Arabic and Korean, which are linguistically distant languages from different origins. As a result, most models struggled to provide comprehensible feedback on the translated texts. Among the various models, ChatGPT showed strong performance in providing feedback in both Arabic and Korean. Since the focus of this study is on developing an instructional design rather than comparing different models, ChatGPT was selected as the sole model used in the study.

The research will adopt a mixed-methods approach, combining a quantitative approach to measure the improvement in performance, and a qualitative approach to understand the individual experiences of the students and the impact of the feedback.

This paper also aims to address the following research questions:

- 1) What is the impact of ChatGPT's feedback on students' performance?
- 2) Are the students satisfied with ChatGPT's feedback?

2. Literature Review

2.1. ChatGPT in Language Learning and Translation

ChatGPT has demonstrated significant potential in enhancing language acquisition and translation skills. Studies highlight its ability to provide immediate corrections, contextual suggestions, and iterative learning opportunities. For example, Haryanti (2024) identified seven key factors; accuracy, instant feedback, accessibility, customization, engagement, and continuous improvement that contributed to improved translation skills among Indonesian

students. Similarly, Prasetya and Syarif (2023) found that ChatGPT's feedback enhanced learner autonomy and English proficiency, with measurable improvements in test scores and self-assessment accuracy.

However, the tool's effectiveness varies depending on context and application. While ChatGPT excels in lexical complexity and fluency, it often struggles with syntactic accuracy and deeper linguistic nuances. Yoon et al. (2023) noted that untuned ChatGPT feedback tended to be generic, failing to address structural and coherence issues in English learners' writing. Cao and Zhong (2023) further observed that while ChatGPT improved lexical diversity in ESL translations, it was outperformed by human instructors in grammatical precision and overall translation quality. These findings suggest that ChatGPT should complement, rather than replace, traditional teaching methods.

2.2 Feedback Mechanisms: ChatGPT vs. Traditional Methods

Feedback is a cornerstone of language learning, and research has compared the efficacy of computer-generated feedback (CF), teacher feedback (TF), and self-feedback (SF). ChatGPT, as a form of CF, offers advantages such as scalability, 24/7 availability, and personalized responses (Cao & Zhong, 2023; Su et al., 2023). Abdelhalim (2024) emphasized that ChatGPT's feedback is most effective when learners employ self-regulated strategies, such as self-monitoring and iterative revision.

Despite these benefits, limitations persist. Dai et al. (2023) found that ChatGPT's feedback, while linguistically fluent, often lacked depth in metacognitive guidance and tended to be overly optimistic. In contrast, TF was perceived as more reliable and contextually nuanced, though its scalability is constrained by time and resource limitations (Zou et al., 2023). Meanwhile, SF fosters critical thinking but may be ineffective for low-proficiency learners (Srichanyachon, 2011). The debate over the superiority of CF or TF remains unresolved, with some studies favoring TF for grammatical accuracy (Park, 2019) and others advocating for AI-assisted CF in error reduction (Sistani & Tabatabaei, 2023).

2.3. Cultural and Pedagogical Considerations

The effectiveness of feedback is also shaped by cultural and educational contexts. Alfayyadh (2016) compared feedback practices in Saudi and U.S. translation programs, finding that Saudi classrooms favored collective, oral feedback, while U.S. institutions prioritized individualized, written critiques. This underscores the need for culturally adaptive AI feedback models. Additionally, Al-Sofi and Abouabdulqader (2020) argued that bilingualism alone is insufficient for effective translation, cultural competence is equally critical, a dimension where ChatGPT may fall short without proper tuning.

2.4. Learner Autonomy and Internal Feedback

Internal feedback, generated when learners compare their work with external references, is crucial for self-regulated learning (Nicol, 2021). ChatGPT can stimulate this process by

providing reference points for comparison. Studies suggest that learners who actively engage with ChatGPT's feedback demonstrate improved self-assessment skills (Lo, 2023; Abdelhalim, 2024). However, challenges arise when students lack the metacognitive skills to critically evaluate AI-generated suggestions, leading to over-reliance or misapplication of feedback (Narciss et al., 2022).

3. Study Design

This study will implement an improved instructional design of the previously suggested by (Hasan et al. 2025), then it will assess the design by conducting a pre-and post-assessments, as well as, an online survey based on Kirkpatrick's model of evaluation (Reaction, Learning, Behavior and Results), as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Evaluation Key Points of the Instructional Design Based on Kirkpatrick's Model

Level	Evaluation Category	Evaluation Key Points
Reaction	Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rate the objectives clarity
	Course Material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rate the difficulty level of the material Rate the usefulness of the material
	Assignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rate feedback provided by ChatGPT Identify Strengths of ChatGPT Identify limitations of ChatGPT
	Time and Facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rate the facilities Rate time efficiency of the class Rate time efficiency of the discussion Identify discussion type preference
	Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rate motivation to continue using the design
Learning	Improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-and post-assessments
Behavior	Learning Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify challenges of translation Identify improvements after learning
Results	Direct results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are the targeted outcomes achieved?

3.1. Procedure:

Figure 1 illustrates the procedure of implementing the new instructional design and its time frame.

Figure 1 Timeframe of the Instructional Design's Implementation and Evaluation

In the first week students' translation skills will be assessed before implementing the new instructional design by providing them with list of sentences that have to translate from Arabic to Korean.

Over a period of eight weeks, practice, online assignment and discussion will take place. A total of 45 minutes a week; 50% of the face-to-face classes will be allocated for actual practice on translation. During this phase, students will not be allowed to use any electronic devices. Instead, they will be provided with vocabulary list prepared by the instructor. Then students will be assigned to use ChatGPT to get feedback on their own translation. In the assignment, the students are required to state prompts entered to get the feedback, ChatGPT's output and their overall opinion. Then students will discuss with the instructor ChatGPT's output (as shown in Figure 2).

Figure 2 Three-stage Instructional Design for Translation Class

In the final week, a post-test and an online survey will be conducted to assess students' improvement in translation skills and their satisfaction with the instructional design.

3.2. Participants

To ensure the homogeneity of the participants, thirty-three students (31 female and 2 male) enrolled in the Korean and English program at the University of Jordan took part in the survey as well as the pre- and post-assessments. All participants had been studying Korean for four years and were considered to be at an intermediate proficiency level.

3.3. Material

The instructional materials progressed in a gradual and structured manner. The process began with simple sentences in Arabic and gradually increased in difficulty by incorporating complex sentences across both formal and informal contexts. This was followed by paragraph-level translations, and ultimately, full texts and official documents were introduced. In addition, students were provided with specific guidelines on how to enter appropriate prompts when using ChatGPT. These guidelines were as follows:

1. Enter detailed and clear prompts

Example: "I translated 'SOURCE TEXT' from Arabic into Korean as 'TARGET TEXT.' Check if there are errors and analyze them, if they exist."

2. Request further clarification when needed

If the output is unclear, students are encouraged to ask for further explanation or request the explanation in a different language.

Example: "Explain it again in Arabic."

3. Specify the type of translation (literal or paraphrased)

Example: "I translated 'SOURCE TEXT' into 'TARGET TEXT' by paraphrasing it and considering cultural differences. Please check whether it is correct."

4. Indicate the formality of the context

Example: "Note: the context of the translation is formal."

5. Clarify the language register (spoken or written)

Example: "I translated 'SOURCE TEXT' into Korean spoken language."

4. Evaluation

After the 8 weeks of implementation, the design was evaluated based on Kirkpatrick's model (Reaction, learning, behavior and results) as follows:

Reaction

A total of 33 students participated in the online survey. The students' satisfaction was evaluated in relation to the instructional design's objectives, materials, time efficiency, facilities, and areas for improvement.

Figure 3 Student Satisfaction Survey Results

As shown in Figure 3, 96.9% of the students stated that the objectives of the instructional design are clear and easy to understand. Regarding the learning materials, students rated the difficulty level on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = very difficult, 5 = very easy). The results showed that 39% of students rated the material as moderately difficult, indicating that the materials used in class were considered manageable. When asked whether the material was useful for improving their translation skills, 81% rated it as “very useful” on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = not useful at all, 5 = very useful). 100% of the students found the classroom convenient and the board clear, indicating no issues with classroom facilities. 72.7% of students agreed that the class time was sufficient to practice translation, meanwhile, 81.8% felt that 45 minutes were enough to discuss ChatGPT’s feedback in class. 93.9% expressed the need to discuss ChatGPT’s output during class sessions.

Figure 4 Perceived Strengths of ChatGPT Feedback

Figure 4 illustrates the ratings related to the feedback provided by ChatGPT (1 = not useful at all, 5 = very useful). The results showed that 68.5% of students were satisfied with the output. In terms of the strengths of the feedback, 75.8% of students highlighted the identification of errors and their types, 66.7% appreciated the quick access to feedback, and another 66.7% valued the provision of improved versions of the translated text. Furthermore, 48.5% noted the clarity and simplicity of the language used in the feedback, 51.5% mentioned the accessibility of feedback regardless of time and location, and 3% pointed to the provision of equivalent vocabulary and useful options.

Figure 5 Perceived Limitation of ChatGPT Feedback

Regarding the question on the limitations of the model, 81.8% of students responded that the model tends to exaggerate when identifying errors. Additionally, 78.8% reported that the model provides contradictory outputs. For example, 48.5% mentioned the inconsistency of responses depending on different prompts, while 42.4% expressed concerns about the low credibility of the model's analysis (As shown in Figure 5).

Table 2: Preferred Feedback Source

Feedback Source	Percentage
Both ChatGPT and Instructor	66%
Only Instructor	27.4%
Only ChatGPT	6%

Table 2 presents the preferred feedback source by students. 66% of students indicated that they preferred receiving feedback from both ChatGPT and the instructor. Meanwhile, 27.4% preferred to receive feedback exclusively from the instructor, and only 6% preferred to receive feedback solely from ChatGPT.

Lastly, the students were asked whether they preferred to continue learning in this way. A total of 81.1% expressed motivation to continue learning translation using this instructional design. Additionally, 54.5% indicated that they would like to incorporate other AI-based models, such as Deepseek, into the learning process.

Learning

Pre- and post-assessments were conducted at the beginning and end of the designed period. These tests aimed to determine whether there was a measurable improvement in the students' translation skills. The material used for the assessment includes both simple and complex sentences (as shown in Table 3).

Table 3 Materials used in Pre-and Post-assessments

Source Language	Target Language
تلك الفتاة الجميلة طويلة That beautiful girl is tall.	그 예쁜 여자가 키가 커요.
تلك الفتاة جميلة وطويلة That girl is beautiful and tall.	그 여자는 예쁘고 키가 커요.
تلك الفتاة الجميلة تدرس اللغة الكورية That beautiful girl studies Korean.	그 예쁜 여자는 한국어를 공부해요.
رأيت تلك الفتاة الجميلة I saw that beautiful girl.	저는 그 예쁜 여자를 봤어요.
قال حسن بأن تلك الفتاة الجميلة تدرس اللغة الكورية Hasan said that the beautiful girl studies Korean.	하산 씨는 그 예쁜 여자가 한국어를 공부한다고 했어요.
رأى حسن الفتاة التي ترتدي القبعة Hasan saw the girl who is wearing the hat.	하산 씨는 모자를 쓴 여자를 봤어요.
لم يأت حسن اليوم بسبب الزكام Hasan didn't come today because of a cold.	오늘 하산 씨는 감기 때문에 못 왔어요.
لم يأت حسن اليوم لأنه مصاب بالزكام Hasan didn't come today because he has a cold.	오늘 하산 씨는 감기에 걸려서 못 왔어요.
أتى حسن اليوم على الرغم من إصابته بالزكام Hasan came today despite having a cold.	감기에 걸렸는데도 하산 씨는 오늘 왔어요.
وفقا لحسن فإن الفتاة الطويلة تدرس اللغة الكورية According to Hasan, the tall girl studies Korean.	하산 씨에 따르면 키가 큰 여자는 한국어를 공부하고 있어요.

During the assessments, students were not allowed to use any electronic devices. They were given 30 minutes to complete the translation task. As shown in Figure 1, the pre-assessment was conducted in the first week, while the post-assessment took place in the eighth week. A total of 33 students participated in both the pre- and post-assessments. Table 4 presents the error ratios in both tests.

Table 4. Error Ratios in Translation Pre-Assessment vs Post-Assessment

	Pre-assessment	Post-assessment
Sentence Order	23 (69.7%)	8 (24.2%)
Grammar	21 (63.6%)	10 (30.3%)
Distinguishing between Formal and Informal	5 (15.1%)	2 (5%)

Sentence order errors were the most frequent in the pre-assessment (69.7 %) but fell sharply to 24.2 % in the post-assessment. These errors appeared mainly in phrases containing adjectives. For example, “beautiful girl” was rendered literally in Korean as “여자가 예쁜” (“girl beautiful”), preserving the Arabic word order. A similar pattern emerged in clauses with the relative pronoun who; for instance, “the girl who is wearing the hat” was translated as “여자 모자를 쓴” (“girl hat wear”). Likewise, “that beautiful girl studies Korean” became “예쁜 여자가 공부해요 한국어를.”

Grammar-related errors accounted for 63.6 % of the pre-assessment but dropped to 30.3 % in the post-assessment. A typical mistake was translating “the girl who’s wearing a hat” as “모자를 쓰는 여자” (“girl who wears a hat”), where the past tense of wear is required. Another example is “Hasan didn’t come today because of a cold,” which some students rendered as “하산 씨는 감기에 걸리기 때문에 오늘 못 왔어요.” The connective “-기 때문에” must be combined with the past tense ending “-았/었-”, and the same constraint applies to “(으)니까” in sentences such as “하산 씨는 감기에 걸리니까 오늘 못 왔어요.”

Errors involving the choice between formal and informal register were less common; 15.1 % in the pre-assessment and 5.0 % in the post-assessment. Correctly gauging context is essential for selecting the appropriate register, yet some students used constructions reserved for highly formal written Korean such as “(으)로 인해” in everyday sentences (e.g., “Hasan didn’t come today because of a cold”).

A paired-samples t-test confirmed these improvements (Table 5). Sentence-order errors declined significantly, $t(32) = 5.16$, $p = 0.00012$, and grammar errors also showed a significant reduction, $t(32) = 4.00$, $p = 0.00035$. In contrast, the reduction in formal/informal errors was not statistically significant, $t(32) = 1.79$, $p = 0.083$, probably because the initial error rate in this category was already low.

Table 5 T-Test Results: Pre-Assessment vs. Post-Assessment

	Pre-assessment (<i>N</i> ₁ =33)		Post-assessment (<i>N</i> ₂ =33)		<i>DF</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
Sentence Order	0.66	0.479	0.212	0.415	32	5.16	<0.001
Grammar	0.69	0.467	0.364	0.487	32	4.00	<0.001
Distinguishing between	0.152	0.364	0.061	0.242	32	1.76	>0.001

Formal and Informal							
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Behavior

Students were asked to identify the challenges they face when translating from Arabic to Korean. They were then required to indicate the categories in which they believed they had improved after the instructional period, during which ChatGPT was used as a feedback provider.

Table 6 Perceived Degree of Difficulty and Improvement

	Degree of Difficulty (%)	Degree of Improvement (%)
Vocabulary	57.6	81.1
Sentence Order	66.7	75.8
Grammar	27.3	54.5
Distinguishing between Spoken and Written languages	48.5	48.5
Distinguishing between Formal and Informal	15.2	27.3

In Table 6, sentence order, vocabulary, distinguishing between the spoken language and the written language, grammar, and differentiating between formal and informal language were identified as challenges students face when translating from Arabic into Korean. However, the students reported that, through ChatGPT’s feedback, vocabulary improved the most (81.1%), followed by sentence order (75%). This indicates that ChatGPT helped them address the most challenging categories and contributed to their improvement.

4. Findings

Integrating students’ perceived improvements with measurable gains from the pre- and post-assessments clearly demonstrates that the revised instructional design is both pedagogically effective and practically applicable in translation classes. The quantitative results, showing significant reductions in sentence-order and grammar-related errors, align with students’ self-reported progress in vocabulary and syntactic awareness. Together, these outcomes underscore the value of embedding ChatGPT into translation pedagogy as a feedback tool.

However, to ensure its optimal impact, it remains crucial to critically evaluate both the strengths and limitations of this approach when implementing it.

One of the primary strengths of using ChatGPT in translation instruction lies in its capacity to provide immediate and convenient access to feedback. As a cloud-based tool, ChatGPT can be accessed anytime and anywhere via mobile phones, tablets, or computers. This aligns with findings by Cao and Zhong (2023), who noted that scalability and accessibility are key advantages of computer-generated feedback (CF). It also supports autonomous learning, reinforcing Abdelhalim's (2024) observation that students who engage actively with AI feedback develop stronger self-regulation skills. Within blended or hybrid learning environments, where students are expected to work independently outside the classroom, this level of accessibility enhances learner engagement and promotes sustained interaction with the target language.

Another significant strength of ChatGPT is its ability to identify and classify translation errors with a degree of precision that supports learner development. The model not only pinpoints the location of an error but also categorizes its type and explains the underlying linguistic rules. For instance, in the sentence “대통령이 계엄령을 내리 때문에 탄핵되었다,” ChatGPT accurately identified the erroneous verb form “내리 때문에” and provided a correction, noting that it should be conjugated as “내렸기 때문에.” This type of detailed error analysis mirrors what Zou et al. (2023) described as the contextual nuance of teacher feedback (TF), suggesting that while ChatGPT cannot fully replicate human expertise, it approximates it in specific grammatical contexts.

In addition to error identification, ChatGPT consistently offers improved versions of student translations, even without explicit prompting. For example, it suggested the corrected sentence “대통령이 계엄령을 내렸기 때문에 탄핵되었다,” providing learners with an immediate model of accurate target-language usage. This iterative exposure aligns with Haryanti (2024)'s emphasis on continuous improvement as a critical factor in developing translation competence. Furthermore, ChatGPT's multilingual capabilities; allowing explanations in students' preferred language reduce cognitive load and facilitate deeper comprehension of complex grammatical and syntactic concepts. Such affordances may particularly benefit learners navigating between linguistically and culturally distant languages like Arabic and Korean.

The flexibility of accessing feedback outside traditional classroom settings also emerged as a notable advantage. As 81.1% of students reported motivation to continue using the instructional design, and 54.5% expressed interest in incorporating additional AI models such as DeepSeek, these findings suggest a strong learner receptivity to AI-assisted translation pedagogy. This resonates with Prasetya and Syarif's (2023) findings on ChatGPT fostering learner autonomy and engagement through scalable feedback mechanisms.

However, despite these strengths, several limitations were identified that warrant careful

consideration. One recurrent issue is the model's tendency toward over-detection of errors, particularly when student prompts were vague or lacked specificity. In such cases, ChatGPT sometimes generated alternative translations and flagged them as corrections, even when the original was acceptable. This tendency can undermine learner confidence and reduce the perceived reliability of feedback, echoing Dai et al. (2023)'s concern about AI-generated feedback lacking metacognitive depth. The study found that these limitations were partially mitigated when students engaged in instructor-led discussions to contextualize and validate ChatGPT's output, reinforcing the critical role of human oversight.

A further limitation involved contradictory analyses of identical input. During classroom discussions, it became evident that ChatGPT sometimes evaluated the same lexical choices differently for different students, even within identical contexts. For example, in translating "Mansaf is served on special occasions," the expression "제공되다" ("to be provided") was flagged as overly literal in one instance but accepted as correct in another. This inconsistency, also noted by Yoon et al. (2023) in relation to untuned ChatGPT feedback, highlights the model's sensitivity to prompt formulation. Refining prompts, for instance, by adding qualifiers such as "if errors exist" was shown to reduce such variability. This finding underscores both the potential and the limitations of AI in pedagogical contexts, aligning with Abdelhalim's (2024) emphasis on the importance of self-regulated strategies and instructor mediation.

The variability of ChatGPT's responses based on prompt phrasing also presents challenges for instructors managing classroom discussions. Since different students may receive divergent feedback for similar translations, unifying class-wide explanations can become complex. This issue resonates with Grassini's (2023) concern about equitable access to AI tools and consistent learning experiences. Without careful moderation, such variability could inadvertently perpetuate confusion rather than resolve it.

Finally, while ChatGPT demonstrates strong linguistic capabilities, it cannot yet be considered fully reliable for handling cultural nuances and pragmatic subtleties. As Al-Sofi and Abouabdulqader (2020) argue, effective translation requires not only bilingual proficiency but also cultural competence, a dimension in which AI tools remain limited. ChatGPT's inability to detect culturally inappropriate translations or idiomatic misinterpretations reinforces the necessity of instructor intervention to ensure the cultural appropriateness and contextual relevance of translated texts.

In conclusion, the revised instructional design demonstrates considerable potential to enhance translation pedagogy by integrating ChatGPT as a feedback mechanism. Its strengths: immediate feedback, detailed error analysis, and fostering learner autonomy offer a promising supplement to traditional instructional methods. However, its limitations; over-detection of errors, contradictory analyses, and challenges in addressing cultural and pragmatic aspects highlight the importance of instructor-led discussions and careful implementation. Consistent

with Park (2019)'s findings favoring human feedback for grammatical precision, this study suggests that ChatGPT should not be seen as a replacement for teachers but as a valuable complementary tool that, when moderated effectively, can enrich the translation learning experience.

5. Conclusion

Adapting to the recent shift in translation pedagogy driven by the emergence of AI based models, this study proposes an instructional design for Arabic Korean translation classes that leverages ChatGPT's feedback. In this design, students practice translation under guidance, use ChatGPT to obtain feedback, and then discuss the model's output in class. This three-stage approach (practice, assignment, and discussion) significantly improved students' translation skills, as reflected in survey and pre /post assessments. Participants expressed high satisfaction with the course materials, facilities, class duration, and the incorporation of an AI based model into their assignments; they also expressed a willingness to continue studying translation through this design.

However, the variety of feedback, contradictory analyses of identical inputs, and limited credibility of some responses sometimes caused confusion. Instructor-led discussion is therefore essential to resolve these ambiguities.

This instructional design is expected to have a long-term impact on translation pedagogy, especially as traditional approaches become untenable amid growing reliance on AI based models for translation tasks. Further research is needed to develop innovative designs that help students maximize the benefits of AI while avoiding over reliance on these systems.

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